

Experimental validation of a novel modelling technique for packed bed thermal storage systems containing non-spherical phase change material capsules

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a novel modeling technique for non-spherical capsule-shaped latent heat packed bed storage (PBS) systems aiming for resource efficiency in iterative optimization and design. The current simulation methods for such systems are resource-intensive and not suitable for iterative design. To address this, it is proposed to combine an efficient approach of detailed simulations of a single capsule during the phase change process with a one-dimensional (1D) model. Finite element simulations are used to capture local phenomena and characterize heat transfer rates from the capsules. The resulting heat flux dataset is integrated into a finite volume model to simulate the entire PCM-PBS system effectively. By combining these approaches, the computational resources needed are significantly reduced while maintaining accuracy. Experimental validation was conducted using a PCM-PBS setup with steel cans containing stearic acid and water as the heat transfer fluid. The results were able to reproduce the temperature history measured at four locations within the packed bed as well as the outlet temperature and total energy remove from the system during discharge for six separate experiments. These confirm the effectiveness of this simulation technique and provide validation. It addresses a knowledge gap in both experimental and numerical aspects, offering potential improvements in charge/discharge rate, energy density, and cost-effectiveness of PCM-PBS systems.

1. Introduction

Low temperature thermal energy storage (TES) plays an important role in both residential and industrial energy systems. Many authors have proposed the use of phase change materials (PCMs) to improve the energy density of low temperature TES units. However, it has proven challenging to design a system which provides both an energy density advantage, sufficient discharge rate, and a reasonable cost of implementation. Commonly selected low temperature PCMs typically have low thermal conductivities. As heat is extracted from the low temperature thermal storage, PCM solidifies on the heat transfer surfaces and conduction through this solid layer dominates heat transfer. This is often referred to as the “rate problem” [1].

One possible solution to the rate problem is to subdivide the PCM in small capsules and then form a packed bed of these capsules. This creates a large surface area between the PCM and the heat transfer fluid (HTF),

while also reducing the length of the largest conduction path. The literature contains several examples of experimental studies of PCM packed bed storages (PBS), with many material variations in terms of PCM and HTF depending on the application and more importantly on the temperature levels in the system. Although additional examples exist for high temperature latent storage using smaller particles, high conductivity PCM and air as HTF, the authors will focus the review and discussion on low temperature systems similar to the one used in this study, in which the most common HTF is water, as presented in Table 1.

A PCM-PBS consisting of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) spherical capsules (diameters: $d_i = 24.5$ mm and $d_o = 26.1$ mm) filled with paraffin wax (two different materials with melting temperatures $T_m = 3.64$ °C and $T_m = 6.81$ °C) in a cylindrical tank 220 mm in diameter and 173 mm high was experimentally tested by [2]. Another PBS consisting of plastic spherical capsules (d_i is not stated and $d_o = 31.8$ mm) filled with paraffin wax ($T_m = 60$ °C) in a cylindrical tank 200 mm in diameter

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and 600 mm high was experimentally tested by [3]. The HTF was air. In this study, the temperature evolution of air and PCM within the bed during the charging mode was investigated. Initially, both temperatures increased at the same rate, but later the air temperature exceeded that of the PCM, indicating thermal equilibrium. Comparison of measured and predicted transient material temperatures at two locations within the bed showed excellent agreement. The effect of air mass flow rate (Re) on bed temperature was observed, with higher Re resulting in a shorter time to reach thermal saturation. During the discharging mode, the entering cooled air caused a temperature drop in the PCM slightly above ambient temperature, in line with both predicted and measured values.

A PCM-PBS consisting of 264 HDPE spherical capsules ($d_i = 53.4$ mm and $d_o = 55$ mm) filled with paraffin wax ($T_m = 60$ °C) also in a cylindrical tank of 360 mm in diameter and 460 mm high was tested experimentally in [4]. Temperature profiles of the HTF and PCM were analyzed during charging with different HTF inlet temperatures and flow rates. Mass flow rate had minimal impact on charging rate when HTF temperature was constant, as surface resistance was negligible compared to resistance inside PCM capsules. Heat transfer rate increased with increases in HTF inlet temperature. Continuous and batchwise discharging experiments were conducted for both sensible heat storage (SHS) and combined storage systems. The combined storage system outperformed the conventional SHS system, which involved direct mixing of HTF with hot water in the storage tank.

A PCM-PBS consisting of commercially produced spherical capsules filled with PK6 manufactured by Rubitherm GmbH (d_i is not stated, $d_o = 3.6$ mm, and $T_m = 3-7$ °C) still in a cylindrical tank 101 mm in diameter and 500 mm high was experimentally tested in [5]. Various parameters such as thermocline analysis, energy efficiency, exergy efficiency, mix number, stratification number, and Richardson number were used to characterize and compare stratification. The addition of PCM packed bed reduced stratification during charging, while similar thermal stratification was observed during discharging. A hybrid latent and sensible storage, combining a small PCM-PBS with a stratified water tank was tested for charging experiments only [6]. The packed bed of 120 HDPE spherical capsules ($d_i = 71$ mm and $d_o = 75$ mm) filled with a commercial PCM called OM48 ($T_m = 45-50$ °C) was held in a small section of a 400 mm diameter and 1000 mm high cylindrical tank. The authors found that higher HTF inlet temperature reduced overall charging time due to improved heat transfer rates. To optimize the combined TES system, PCM selection should prioritize properties like large latent heat capacity, similar specific heat capacity to water, and higher thermal conductivity. A PCM-PBS consisting of 9170 stainless-steel spherical capsules ($d_i = 41$ mm and $d_o = 42$ mm) filled with paraffin wax ($T_m = 67-69$ °C) in a cylindrical 900 mm diameter and 1100 mm high tank was experimentally tested in [7]. Charging and discharging were done separately using water as HTF. The study introduced a PCM-water tank concept to enhance energy storage capacity, resulting in a 29.6 % improvement compared to a conventional water tank. During charging, the PCM-water tank exhibited faster temperature rise, longer charging time, and reduced power near the PCM phase change temperature. Stratification in the PCM-water tank was less effective due to latent heat and capsule shell conductivity, particularly noticeable at lower flow rates. However, the PCM-water tank demonstrated an advantage in

discharging power and outlet temperature, making it suitable for applications with low flow rates. It enables the release of a larger quantity of qualified hot water, despite lower discharging energy efficiency.

Finally, one study looked at experimentally testing a hybrid latent and sensible storage using a packed bed of 95 tin-plated steel cans (d_i is not stated, $d_o = 53.2$ mm, and the length $L = 70$ mm) filled with $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ ($T_m = 55$ °C) stacked in 5 layers of 10 cans held in a cylindrical tank 290 mm in diameter and 350 mm high [8]. This study established heat-transfer correlations for computer modeling of a PCM system through thermal tests for heat-transfer coefficients during charging and discharging. A non-dimensional heat-transfer ratio captured overall coefficient changes over time. The Goncalves number indicated improved heat transfer during charging as phase-change progressed. Discharge mode showed increased heat-transfer effectiveness with higher Reynolds numbers.

All but one of these experimental works is focused on the use of spherical capsules. For macroscale capsules, there is little justification for exclusively using spherical capsules over alternative shapes. For instance, studies have shown that for equal volumes, various shapes exhibit superior surface area to volume ratios compared to spheres [9]. Specifically, ellipsoidal capsules have been found to, in some cases, possess higher surface area to volume ratios and packing densities in comparison to spheres under similar high border effects and random packing conditions [10–12]. The rate of heat transfer from the capsules to the HTF is a strong function of the surface area per unit volume of the packed bed. It is conceivable that this increase in the heat transfer rate could be useful for applications with high discharge rates. Or perhaps optimizing the shape could allow for the same surface area per unit volume with larger capsules. The cost of packed bed systems is a strong function of the number of capsules used rather than total size or volume, and the manufacturing cost of each capsule. So, even moderately increasing the size of capsules or reducing the manufacturing complexity of each capsule may result in useful reductions in system cost. One of the main reasons to look at cylindrical capsules is related to the reduced manufacturing cost; cans of all size are manufactured each day in large quantities at low prices by the canning industry.

The techniques for fully simulating PCM-PBS are well established in the literature. A fully coupled finite volume simulation combined with a method of simulating the packed bed (e.g. discrete element method) can be used to fully predict the behaviour of these systems [13,14]. However, these types of simulation are very resource intensive and poorly suited to iterative design work. For the purposes of optimizing storage systems, a more efficient simulation technique is desirable. Several authors have published such models on PCM packed bed systems which utilize spherical capsules. The basic premise of these simulation techniques can be traced back to Shumman [15] who developed a simple method for simulating packed beds for sensible storage in 1929. Methods based broadly on Shumman simulate the storage as a one-dimensional, two-phase system with one phase being the HTF and other being the solid component of the packed bed. The two phases are coupled using an empirically determined convection coefficient [16–23].

In latent systems, the conduction through the body of the solid phase (from one capsule to the adjacent capsule by direct conduction) is often

Table 1
Summary of previous experimental work on PCM packed beds utilizing low temperature PCMs.

	Capsule Shape	Capsule Diameter d_o	PCM	Melting Temperature T_m	Packing density
Cho and Choi [2]	Sphere	26.1 mm	paraffin wax	3.64 °C and 6.81 °C	0.53
Benmansour et al. [3]	Sphere	31.8 mm	paraffin wax	60 °C	0.594
Nallusamy et al. [4]	Sphere	55 mm	paraffin wax	60 °C	0.5
Oro et al.) [5]	Sphere	3.6 mm	PK6	3–7 °C	0.5
Kumar et al. [6]	Sphere	75 mm	OM48	45–50 °C	0.527
He et al. [7]	Sphere	41 mm	paraffin wax	67–69 °C	0.621
Goncalves and Probert [8]	Cylinder	53 mm	$MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	55 °C	0.856*

* Cans were stacked in an ordered pattern instead of being randomly packed making this packing density difficult to compare to the other work.

ignored leading to a 1D transport model for the HTF which is coupled to the PCM capsules via the surface temperature of the capsule and a convection (or overall heat transfer) coefficient. In order to determine the surface temperature of the PCM capsules, a model of the internal temperature distribution is required. Authors have tackled this in several different ways. The simplest approach has been to utilize a lumped capacitance model [19]. This is only valid for small Bi numbers and therefore is only applicable to very small capsules. An extended Biot number approach for spherical and cylindrical capsules was presented in [24]. However, this method requires an analytical solution of the capsule in question and therefore cannot be easily generalized to include different shapes.

Alternatively, authors have used a one-dimensional numerical conduction model, which includes a phase change modelling approach (enthalpy method, modified C_p method, etc.) to predict the temperature distribution in the capsules. However, this approach is only directly applicable to spherical capsules [17,21], either during discharging where conduction heat transfer dominates, or in smaller capsules where natural convection could be neglected. A similar approach could be taken for alternative capsule shapes, but it would require a 2D or 3D numerical model. Such an approach was taken in [25] where a quasi-2D model of a cylindrical capsule was first modelled to validate the numerical results to experimental measurements. Then a packed bed with spherical capsule similar to [23] was studied. A spherical capsule filled with PCM was modelled in 3D, accounting for natural convection during charging, and an overall heat transfer coefficient was obtained as a function of the state of charge of the capsule. Then a Shumman type two-phase model was applied to determine local packed bed temperature over time. Even with the more accurate 3D simulations on the spherical capsules, the accuracy of this approach was less than what was originally obtained by [23] with a weighted-average approach that mostly made abstraction of the capsules, at a computational cost that is still pretty large for natural convection simulations using the enthalpy-porosity method [26].

Thus, the authors identified a knowledge gap in both experimental and numerical aspects in the development of PCM-PBS utilizing non-spherical capsules. Capsule shape optimization has the potential to improve PCM-PBS systems in terms of charge/discharge rate, energy density and cost effectiveness. The novelty of this work lies in combining detailed but computationally inexpensive simulations of a single non-spherical capsule during the phase change process with a 1D model, allowing the simulation of the entire PCM-PBS system efficiently while maintaining accuracy. Firstly, detailed simulations of a single capsule during the phase change process are performed to capture the local phenomena accurately and extract heat transfer rates because on the HTF temperature and the state of charge of the capsule. Secondly, these detailed simulations are integrated into a 1D model, allowing the simulation of the entire PCM-PBS system efficiently. This combination of approaches significantly reduces the computational resources required while preserving the essential physics of the system compared to the alternative of a complete 3D simulation of the packed bed, including phase change heat transfer in each capsule and 3D flow of the HTF fluid around those capsules. Therefore, this study introduces an innovative modeling technique for PCM-PBS systems featuring non-spherical capsule shapes, aiming to ensure resource efficiency for iterative optimization and design purposes.

Furthermore, to validate the proposed modeling technique, an experimental PCM-PBS setup using cylindrical cans was manufactured and tested. The decision to opt for cylindrical capsules allowed for the exploration of an alternative capsule shape while still capitalizing on an established manufacturing system that can be readily employed for cylindrical capsules, making the entire production process more efficient and cost-effective, in addition to providing a larger surface-to-volume ratio per capsule.

2. Experimental setup

The experimental PCM-PBS was designed and built as a validation experiment and was not optimized for a residential or industrial application. However, the size and aspect ratio of the storage was similar to that which could be used in a residential application, such as domestic hot water. The HTF was water and the PCM chosen was stearic acid. This fatty acid is nontoxic, compatible with the encapsulation material and has a transition temperature ($T_m = 69.3^\circ\text{C}$) which is useful in a number of low temperature applications. Table 2 summarizes the PCM properties.

The core of the experimental setup was a cylindrical acrylic tank which housed a packed bed of 251 PCM capsules. This packed bed was contained in the cylindrical portion of the tank by steel grids at either end. Additionally, the tank was surrounded by a layer of 4 cm thick Armaflex insulation to minimize heat transfer between the tank and the surrounding environment, ensuring accurate temperature control during the experiments. Instrumentation included six resistive temperature detectors (RTDs – PT100 with an uncertainty of $\pm(0.15 + 0.002T)^\circ\text{C}$) and a Coriolis mass flow meter (with an uncertainty of $\pm 1\%$). Four of the RTDs (probes 3–6) were inserted into the packed bed (see Fig. 1). Probes 1 and 2 were located in the inlet and outlet of the storage tank (see Fig. 2 for the full process diagram). Fig. 3 show a photograph of the PCM-PBS and Table 3 summarizes the specifications of the storage.

The PCM capsules were cylindrical tin-plated steel (approximate thermal conductivity of 52 W/m.K) cans filled with stearic acid. The cans are similar to those used in the food processing industry and the tin plating helps improve the corrosion resistance. Fig. 4 shows a photograph of one of the capsules. Table 4 summarize the properties of the capsules.

3. Numerical method

The numerical simulation of the packed bed comprises two parts: a 2D axisymmetric finite element simulation of the PCM capsule using COMSOL Multiphysics 5.3 (see Section 3.1), and an in-house 1D finite volume simulation of the HTF flow within the packed bed. It is important to note that the symmetry assumptions are specific to the 2D model of the individual capsule and do not extend to the 1D simulation of the overall packed bed. The simulation method employed partially decouples the packed bed model and capsule simulation [27].

The overall assumptions made by the model are as follows:

1. Heat transfer in the HTF is only in the axial direction
2. Heat transfer between capsules is negligible
3. Material properties are invariant with changes in temperature or phase
4. Heat transfer rate between the PCM capsule and HTF is dominated by the local HTF temperature and the state of charge of the capsule
5. For a fixed mass flow rate, the convection coefficient does not vary within the packed bed

The governing equation for the HTF is the one-dimensional energy equation (see Eq. (1)). Interaction between the HTF and the capsules is

Table 2
PCM properties.

Phase change temperature (T_m)	69.3 °C
Phase change enthalpy (L)	208 kJ/kg
Density, liquid (ρ_l)	837 kg/m ³
Density, solid (ρ_s)	965 kg/m ³
Thermal conductivity, liquid (k_l)	0.17 W/m.K
Thermal conductivity, solid (k_s)	0.3 W/m.K
Specific heat capacity, liquid (c_{pl})	2322 J/kg.K
Specific heat capacity, solid (c_{ps})	1670 J/kg.K

Fig. 1. Schematic of the storage tank showing the vertical positioning of temperature probes (Probes 1–6), inlet and outlet locations, and key dimensions.

entirely controlled by the source term \dot{Q}_c which is a function of the state of charge (SoC) and temperature of the surrounding HTF (T_{HTF}). The value of the source term is determined via the capsule simulation.

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho C_p u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = k \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \dot{Q}_c(\text{SoC}, T_{HTF}) \quad (1)$$

The left-hand side of Eq. (1) represents the temporal change in the temperature field, including the convective term involving the HTF velocity (u). The right-hand side represents the diffusion term associated with the thermal conductivity of the HTF (k) and the source term (\dot{Q}_c) accounting for heat transfer between the capsules and the HTF. This equation was solved using the finite volume method with an implicit/hybrid differentiation scheme [28].

The hybrid aspect of the differentiation scheme refers to the flexibility of the method to employ different differencing schemes depending on the local flow or solution characteristics. It combines the benefits of both central differencing and upwind differencing schemes. For regions where the flow or gradient is well-behaved, central differencing can be used to provide accurate results. In regions with strong gradients or flow directionality, upwind differencing can be employed to better capture the dominant flow direction and prevent spurious oscillations. By using the finite volume method with an implicit/hybrid differentiation

scheme, the discretized convective and diffusive terms are solved simultaneously as a system of algebraic equations.

The source term \dot{Q}_c accounts for heat transfer between the capsules and the HTF. The 1D finite volume simulation determines the value of \dot{Q}_c using a heat flux data set previously created using the 2D axisymmetric finite element simulation of the PCM capsule.

An example will help to illustrate the modelling process. At the beginning of the discharging phase the storage and capsules are at a uniform temperature of 72.1°C ($T_{initial}$). The tank was then discharged by introducing cold water into the tank at 30°C (T_{in}). As this cold water (HTF) passes through the packed bed it is heated up and exits the tank. Over the course of the discharge process the capsules are exchanging heat with water that falls within a range between $T_{initial}$ and T_{in} . When using the modelling technique to predict the behaviour of this storage, the first step is to carry 2D simulations in COMSOL Multiphysics 5.3 to determine the heat transfer rate at the surface of a single capsule as it is cooled from the initial temperature of the storage to local temperature of the HTF (T_{HTF}). Each individual simulation produces a data set relating the heat transfer rate from the capsule to its SoC for a particular T_{HTF} at every time step. This simulation is then repeated for multiple different values of T_{HTF} (all of which are within that range of $T_{initial} > T_{HTF} > T_{in}$, in this example $72.1^\circ\text{C} > T_{HTF} > 30^\circ\text{C}$). Combining the data from each of these simulations (Q , SoC, and T_{HTF}) the ‘‘Heat Flux Data Set’’ is assembled. Fig. 5 shows an example of this type of data set and this phase of the simulation is shown in the top half of the flow chart presented in Fig. 6.

In Fig. 5, the oscillations at high SoC are an artifact of the time resolution in the capsule simulation and occur due to the rapid rate of melting in the first moment of the simulation, these oscillations smooth out with smaller time steps. However, a sensitivity study showed that at the current time step (maximum 1 s) the results are independent of the time step and the oscillations have negligible impact. The \dot{Q}_c is determined by linearly interpolating within this heat flux data set.

The second phase of the modelling techniques utilizes a 1D finite volume model to simulate the storage. The local HTF temperature (T_{HTF}) and SoC are used to estimate the heat transfer rate between the capsules and the HTF (Q_c). This is done by interpolating in the Heat Flux Data Set which was previously assembled using the capsule model. By numerically solving the heat transfer equations for the tank simulation a complete temperature history of the energy storage can be predicted. The 1D model and therefore the Heat Flux Data Set only utilizes the specifications and properties of the capsule and can therefore be used to model any storage which uses those exact capsules. This phase of the simulation is shown in the bottom half of the flow chart presented in Fig. 6.

3.1. Capsule simulation

The cylindrical PCM capsules were simulated as axisymmetric around the main axis and symmetric along the mid-line (see Fig. 7) modelling both the PCM and the can wall. A finite element simulation was created in COMSOL Multiphysics 5.3. Simulations were run on a workstation with two Intel Xeon E5–2630 v3 (8 cores @ 2.4 GHz, hyperthreaded) and 128 GB of RAM.

The random orientation of the cans within the body of the packed bed makes it nearly impossible to include convection in the simulation without locating and simulating the heat transfer within each capsule individually. This would drastically increase the computational cost of the simulation. Additionally, this simulation is primarily concerned with low temperature heat storage where the discharge (solidification) will be the limiting process. Discharge is typically dominated by conduction through the solid layer of PCM formed on the inside of the capsule, making convection in the melt less significant. For these reasons, capsule simulations were run considering only conduction [29,30]. Given these assumptions, the governing equation is the conductive energy equation

Fig. 2. Process diagram of the experimental setup (Showing Tanks (TK), Temperature Sensors (T), Pressure Sensor (P), Flow Sensor (FR), Valves (V), Pump (PU), Emergency Shut-Off Valve (ESV), Inline Heater (IH), Atmospheric Vent (AV), and Relief Valve (RV)).

(Eq. (2)) which is solved with the boundary conditions as indicated in Fig. 7: one symmetry plane and two equivalent convective boundary conditions on the exposed surface of the can. Phase change was simulated using the modified specific heat method [31]. Within a defined “mushy zone”, the C_p is increased to account for the transition energy of the PCM. The modified $C_{p,eff}(T)$ is defined by Eq. (3) where $D(T)$ is a function which defines how the phase transition is spread over the mushy zone. In these simulation $D(T)$ was a Gaussian function (see Eq. (4)) [26].

$$\rho C_{p,eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) \quad (2)$$

$$C_{p,eff}(T) = C_p + L \cdot D(T) \quad (3)$$

$$D(T) = e^{-\frac{(T-T_m)^2}{(\Delta T/4)^2}} \bigg/ \sqrt{\pi(\Delta T/4)^2} \quad (4)$$

A sensitivity analysis was used to ensure that the predicted heat transfer rate was independent of the size of the mushy zone. Fig. 8 shows an example of this sensitivity study for $T_{HTF}=30^\circ\text{C}$. Similarly, an analog behavior for both mesh size and timestep was found. All capsule simulations presented in this work were completed with a mushy zone ΔT of 3°C , a maximum size of 1 mm and a maximum time step of 1 s.

3.2. Convection coefficient

The convective heat transfer coefficient is a key input for the accurate 2D capsule simulations. A number of correlations exist in the literature for the convection coefficient between a packed bed and HTF [32–37] as presented in Fig. 9. However, they are all capsule shape dependant, and none apply directly to the cylindrical capsules used in the validation experiments presented in this work. Additionally, they seem to have been exclusively created using compressible fluids (gas) as HTF. Consequently, one of the main challenges is to effectively predict

the convection coefficient using existing correlations for non spherical capsules. Even for spherical capsules, there is a large disparity between different correlations.

For the simulations involving cylindrical capsules, a convection coefficient of $200\text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ was selected as an empirical approximation. While the choice of this parameter can be considered a fitting parameter, it was derived based on an averaged approximation of available correlations, knowing the flow rate in the experimental work done by the authors varies from approximately 2.5 to 10 L/min (see Table 5). It is important to emphasize that in this specific configuration used in this study, heat transfer is primarily governed by conduction rather than convection. This is particularly significant due to the presence of a phase change material (PCM) within the system. The dominant mode of heat transfer occurs through conduction within the PCM, making the influence of the convection coefficient on the overall heat transfer process expected to be minimal, as demonstrated in numerous PCM system studied [38–41].

3.3. Storage simulation

The complete storage packed with capsules is modelled based on previously described Eq. (1), through a 1D finite volume model approach to simulate the storage behavior by using the capsule (2D model) results at varying temperatures as the source term. Sensitivity studies were completed on mesh size and timestep for the overall storage model looking at the outlet temperature of the system and are shown on Fig. 10. The studies showed negligible variation of the outlet temperature for both timestep and mesh size and thus the presented results were obtained with a time step of 1 s and a mesh size of 2.5 mm.

4. Validation

4.1. Spherical capsules

Fig. 11 compares the outlet temperature measured in [7] from a

Fig. 3. Photograph of the experimental packed bed.

Table 3
Properties of the storage.

Height	0.7 m
Diameter	0.4 m
Volume	0.011 m ³
# of Capsules	251
Packing Density	0.418

packed bed of spheres with those predicted by the current simulation technique. In this case, the numerical simulation utilizes a heat transfer coefficient predicted by Tsotsas [37].

Agreement is satisfactory considering the uncertainty and limitations of the model and experiment. Predicted outlet temperature curves agree well in shape, with the higher flow rates agreeing better than the lower. However, several issues with the simulation approach and experiment are evident. The experimental results show an immediate drop in the outlet temperature from the start of the presented data. At the beginning of the discharge process, the hot HTF stored in the tank will be pushed out. A sensor at the outlet would then be expected to measure the initial temperature of the tank for a period of time until the sensible storage is exhausted. Thermal processes which could contribute to this discrepancy between the simulation and experiments include mixing of the cold incoming HTF with the stored hot HTF, heat losses from the tank (or piping) to the atmosphere, or the possibility that results from [7] did not include the results from the initial period when the warm HTF is pushed out of the tank. It is unlikely that heat losses are significant enough to create this effect as that the tank was insulated. Given that the packed

Fig. 4. Photograph of the PCM capsule.

Table 4
PCM capsule properties.

Total Height	83 mm
Outer Diameter	53 mm
Wall Thickness	2 mm
Average Total Mass	0.1695 kg
Average PCM Mass	0.1365 kg

Fig. 5. Heat flux data set for a mass flow rate of 581.6 kg/h and $T_{initial}=72.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

bed model is one dimensional there is no reasonable way to implement mixing using this technique. Experimental design issues could also contribute to the disparity between the experiment and simulation. The simulation has a perfect instantaneous start point with a perfectly uniform temperature distribution throughout the system. It is difficult to ensure either of these conditions in an experimental system.

Fig. 6. Flow chart showing how a full simulation is carried out.

4.2. Cylindrical capsules

A total of six discharge scenarios were run experimentally and subsequently simulated using the presented modelling technique. Table 5 summarizes the boundary conditions of each of these simulations. All other simulation inputs follow the experimental setup described in Tables 2–4, including geometry description, packing density and thermophysical properties of PCM and capsules.

To avoid repetition and for practical purposes, Experiment 4 will be used to describe the results in detail first, running the reader through the various steps, and the end results from the other five experiments will be presented compared to the experimental results after.

Fig. 12 presents the temperature measured in the center of the PCM-PBS during the discharge process with a mass flow of 292.9 kg/h (Experiment 4). The solid lines represent the measured values from the experimental setup (probes 3 to 6 as indicated in Figs. 1 and 2) while the dashed lines are those predicted by the simulation. There is reasonable agreement throughout the experiment.

Fig. 13 shows the cumulative energy extracted from the packed bed during the same experiment and corresponding simulation. These energy plots were created by applying conservation of energy to the inlet and outlet temperature measurements and then integrating the heat flux over time (see Eq. (5) and 6).

$$Q(t) = \dot{m}_p(T_{outlet}(t) - T_{inlet}(t)) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 7. Domain of the capsule simulation showing the axis of rotation and symmetry plane.

Fig. 8. Mushy zone sensitivity analysis showing the average heat transfer rate from the capsule for $T_{HTF} = 30^\circ\text{C}$.

$$E_{extracted}(t) = \int_0^t Q(t) dt \quad (6)$$

There is reasonable agreement between the experiment and simulation as well as the theoretical energy storage of the tank. There are two theoretical capacities shown in the figure, one includes the sensible storage of the tank walls ($E_{cap-theory}$) and the other does not ($E_{cap-no tank}$).

Fig. 14 shows the outlet temperature history which was measured in the experimental storage and the equivalent predictions made by the simulation technique for all six different experimental conditions previously described.

Fig. 9. Convection coefficients predicted by selected correlations for the spherical capsules used in [32–37].

Table 5
Summary of experimental parameters.

Experiment	\dot{m} (kg/h)	$T_{initial}$ (°C)	T_{in} (°C)
1	155.2	75.0	41.0
2	167.5	75.1	43.5
3	284.4	75.8	43.0
4	292.9	75.0	43.2
5	581.6	72.1	29.7
6	587.2	73.6	29.5

Although the higher flowrate scenarios (Experiments 3 to 6) show better agreement than the lower flow rate cases, overall, the results show a good agreement between simulations and experiments with a maximum root mean square error (RMSE) of 2 °C when comparing the outlet temperatures in both simulations and experiments. This level of agreement is acceptable for design purposes and these simulations are significantly more resource efficient than a fully dynamic 3D simulation or capsule simulations accounting for natural convection. Requiring the simulation of a single capsule a few dozen times (depending on the specifics of the simulation) rather than simulating a fully coupled PCM-PBS containing hundreds if not thousands of individual capsules. The separation of the capsule simulation and storage simulation allows for additional utility. The 1D storage simulation can be run very quickly (current simulations take <5 min) and is therefore invaluable for sizing. When modifying the capsule, the finite element simulations must be rerun to create a new heat flux data set which takes longer. The time required to run the capsule simulations will depend on the available resources, capsule size, and storage temperature range but the simulations presented here required 3–4 h total.

Fig. 10. Sensitivity analysis for timestep (left) and mesh element size (right) showing the outlet temperature evolution through time for both cases.

5. Conclusion

A novel simulation technique for modeling PCM-PBS systems using non-spherical capsules was presented in this paper. It makes use of *a priori* simulations of heat transfer inside the PCM capsule to obtain heat flux data sets followed by a 1D simulation to determine the temperature change of the HTF as a function of the heat flux data set and SoC of the PCM. The validity of the approach has been demonstrated through experimental validation and comparison with existing literature data.

Fig. 11. Outlet temperature measured by [7] and predicted by the numerical simulation during the discharge process.

Fig. 12. Comparison of the temperatures measured in the storage tank (cylindrical capsules) with those predicted by the simulation. Experimental measurements have an uncertainty of less than ± 0.35 °C; error bars are not shown for clarity.

Fig. 13. Comparison of the energy extracted from the experimental and numerical storages (exp 4).

Fig. 14. Comparison of the outlet temperature measured in all experiments and those predicted by the simulation technique. Experimental measurements have an uncertainty of less than ± 0.35 °C; error bars are not shown for clarity.

For validation, the simulation results were compared with outlet temperature measurements from a packed bed of spherical capsules [7]. The agreement between predicted and measured outlet temperatures was satisfactory. Additionally, experiments were performed with a packed bed of cylindrical capsules and the results compared with simulations. The comparison demonstrated reasonable agreement in temperature profiles within the storage tank, as shown by internal temperature measurements during discharge and cumulative energy extraction presented in detail for one of the experiments. The outlet temperature history also displayed good agreement between experimental and numerical results for each experiment performed.

This modeling technique simplifies the complex reality of PCM-PBS systems but effectively predicts temperature behavior in the packed bed and provides valuable design insights. By separating capsule and storage simulations, the approach achieves resource efficiency for sizing and optimization. However, the modelling of the capsule is limited to conduction dominated heat transfer, which means either modelling the discharge process or melting process of very small capsule with negligible natural convection present. Furthermore, the convection coefficient between the HTF and capsule walls is currently a fitted parameters since correlations are not in place for packed bed flow over non-spherical capsules.

While the modeling technique offers a practical and efficient solution for designing and analyzing PCM-PBS systems, further improvements and optimizations are necessary. Future work will focus on determining

the level of applicability of this approach to melting (charging) cases where natural convection could play a role. Then, focus will be on refining the simulation process and addressing limitations associated with complex capsule shapes and design features.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Benjamin Sponagle: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Simon Maranda:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **William Delgado-Diaz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology. **Remo Waser:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Dominic Groulx:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Jörg Worlitschek:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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